

THE EFFECT OF GROUP GUIDANCE ACTIVITIES IN INAPPROPRIATE STUDENT BEHAVIORS

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Abstract:

The purpose of this study is to research how to solve inappropriate student behaviors that class teachers' encounter, using Group Guidance Activities. This study is an action research. Experimental method is used while doing it. Study group consist of 31 3rd year primary school students. Evaluation tool of this study consists 39 items. Evaluation tool is created based on Likert scale. At the end of this research, it was found that Group Guidance Activities had positive and meaningful impact on students' inappropriate behaviors.

Keywords: guidance, activity, action research, inappropriate behavior

1. Introduction

There are students who come from different socio-economic levels and from different cultural backgrounds and they all have different characteristics they also are sharing the same classroom environment. Because of these differences, it is hard to continue education progress without any problems. By finding and researching students' inappropriate behaviors we can decrease its occurrence to the best it is possible. As results show school environment will become more convenient and problem free for education continue. At these last years it is being observed that more and more people are researching on classroom discipline and management. Results of these observations show that teachers that work in state school spend %75 their time for classroom management and discipline and can only spend %25 of their time for actual education, %54 of teachers expressed that because of students' inappropriate behaviors education was delayed and there is at least some kind of a problem behavior in %60 of primary

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school students (Ataman, 2000). Uncontrolled and undesirable student behaviors in classrooms were approached as a discipline problem for many years and it still is (Erden, 2001). Behavior management, especially choosing right strategies for naturally occurring inappropriate student behaviors gives a very critical role for teachers in classroom management because until now as there was no classroom without any problem behaviors and as these behaviors won't disappear themselves, it tells us that there is a need for teachers to take an action (Turnuklu & Yıldız, 2002).

In modern classroom management models helping and guiding students is highlighted (Adams & Hamm, 1997). In modern education discipline models, the main aim is to make students aware of their behaviors and to teach them the ability of self-management (Tuncer, 1980). Group guidance activities have developing, corrective, protective and adaptive features for student development. It is an important element in modern education programs (Oncu, 1990).

Group guidance is a method used for resolving negative attitudes and behaviors of students for a long time but school consultants who work with big groups don't evaluate the process of guidance and results of them. In the literature scanning done on this topic there are projects found, conducted in Florida and Indiana.

As example for big group guidance experiences that was developed in Florida shows that it was beneficial at 4th grade primary school students. This experiment was repeated again later in Indiana and it showed that big group guidance is an effective way to approach students who have negative attitudes towards school (Myrick, Merhill ve Swanson, 1986). This project may be improved for teachers' need and students' interest. This project is a unique and valuable experience for students who will take group guidance services (Oncu, 1990).

This is a research to find out whether group guidance activities are effective to convert inappropriate student behaviors to appropriate student behaviors or not for primary school students.

2. Method

This is an action research with experimental process. To achieve the results that are shown in other sections, pretest and final test used without a control group. The same group took the pretest and after the program is finished they took the final test. The difference between the pretest and the final test shows how effective is this program.

The study group consists of 31, 3rd year students. Evaluation tool is created based on 3 ways Likert scale (I agree, I am not sure, I don't agree), survey was used. For this tool at first an analysis was made to see the need for inappropriate behaviors. Later on, based on needs a question pool was created. 5 professional program developers with graduate degrees assisted us on that. The evaluation tool consists of 39 items and 3 primal parts.

- 1st part: Inappropriate behaviors towards teachers. (6 items)
- 2nd part: Inappropriate behaviors towards class mates (14 items)
- 3rd part: Inappropriate behaviors towards themselves (19 items)

KR20 Reliability of evaluation tool was found as .91. You can see the plan and stages of the study on the chart below.

Table 1: Study Plan and its Stages

Activities	Date	Materials	Responsible	Explanation
Material named "Me When I Enter This Class"	1.12.2016	Drawing block, paintings, glue etc.	Counselor Teacher, Parents.	The visual material was made and put on the classroom door (When you enter this classroom you are valuable, you are loved, you are tolerant, you are mathematician, poet and writer but most importantly you are happy!)
Material named " We are in the classroom"	5.12.2016	Drawing block, paintings, glue etc.	Counselor Teacher, Parents.	In our classroom: We now and respect our differences, we are building trust, we are kind to each other, we support each other, we thank each other. (Material was made and put.)
Material named "My teacher"	6.12.2016	Drawing block, paintings, glue etc.	Counselor Teacher, Parents (this visual was gifted to the teacher)	When you ask me how I feel, when you listen to me, when you are smiling at me, when you greet me, I feel valuable. (Material was made and put.)
Parent information conference	7.12.2016	Projection.	Counselor and Classroom Teachers, Parents	In this conference the aims of the Project and how to use the blogs was showed.
I am learning classroom rules.	12.12.2016	Classroom rules copies, computer, projection.	Counselor Teacher	Purpose: To teach what are the classroom rules and what are the consequences for not obeying them. Time:40 minutes.

Activities	Date	Materials	Responsible	Explanation
Compliment Game	28.12.2016	Small, colored papers and a box to put them in.	Counselor Teacher	Purpose: To learn that we have differences from each other. Time:40 minutes.
Let's make our own tree	4.01.2017	Colored papers, Drawing block, glue, scissors.	Counselor Teacher	Students drew trees on colored papers then they added their positive aspects on them using small papers.
We make the rules together.	11.01.2017	A4 sheets	Counselor Teacher	As a whole class, we decided the classroom rules.
How to spend our semester vacation?	20.01.2017	Blogger site	Counselor Teacher	Previously created bulletin uploaded on to blogger for parents.

How do I see myself?	6.02.2017	Forms.	Counselor Teacher	Friends introduce each other and they fill a friendship form.
I made my own toy.	9.02.2017	Any suitable material	Students and parents	Students and parents made their own toys and everybody shared them with each other.
I am glad that you are my friend	14.02.2017	Heart shaped papers	Counselor Teacher	Students wrote thank you notes to each other using heart shaped papers.

Activities	Date	Materials	Responsible	Explanation
Don't break heart	21.02.2017	Heart shaped papers	Counselor Teacher	What makes you feel sad? After every word that heart is wrinkled What makes you feel better? After these words the heart is flattened
I can control my anger.	6.03.2017	I can control my anger, poems and drawings	Project founder Counselor Teacher	Poems and drawings are created and presented.
My dream school	All notebooks were completed at 24.03.2017	My dream school notebook.	Counselor Teacher	Notebooks were given to students for them to describe their dream school in it.
What happened to the apple?	30.03.2017	2 apples	Counselor Teacher	Analogy technique was used. Good and bad phrases were told to apples and the difference was examined.
I can control my anger competition results	4.04.2017	Medals and certificates.	Project founder Counselor Teacher	Medals and certificates were given to students.
Tolerance Envoy	10.4.2017	Tolerance Envoy Cards	Counselor Teacher	Selection of students with tolerant behavior.
I learned that.	18.4.2017	Cards	Counselor Teacher	Students wrote what they have learned from this project on to cards and we made a video.

3. Results

Before the study, using a pretest inappropriate behavior level of the group was determined. Group guidance activities that aim to change these behaviors were used. In order to widespread these activities a blogger site was created to track parents and students. Activities were shared under Information and Communication section. Comments and feedbacks were also taken from parents and students. On 24.04.2017 there were 1642 views and 43 comments on the blogger site.

Parents, students and teachers who joined this project seemed satisfied with the activities. Feedbacks taken from face to face interactions and comments on the site supports that. School administration supported and encouraged this project.

As it can be seen on the chart below students' pre-test arithmetic mean value is 80.90 and their standard deviation is 9.47. After the final test, their arithmetic mean value is 108.55 and their standard deviation 5.54

Table 2: Pretest- Final Test arithmetic mean and standard deviation values

	Mean	N	Deviation
Pretest	80,90	31	9,47
Final test	108,55	31	5,54

After finishing this program, we can see that there is a visible increase in students' mean scores. Scores increased to 108.55 from 80.90. On the Chart 3 there is t-test result to understand the increase in their scores better and more meaningful.

Table 3: Pretest Final test t-test results

	Mean	Deviation	t	Independence	Meaningfulness
Pretest – Final test	-27,64	11,29	-13,62	30	,000*

As it can be seen on the chart 2 increase in the mean score of the students was tested as .005 and it was found meaningful. ($t(30)=-13,62$; $p<,05$). Otherwise we can say that based on these results the program had positive effect on students. In order to understand which parts of the program was effective, pretest and final test parts of the evaluation tool was also examined. There are mean results of them below.

a) 1st part: Inappropriate behaviors towards teachers

1. He/She listens to warnings made by teacher, increased to 2.58 from 2.10,
2. He/She will not speak unless he has permission from his teachers, increased to 2,40 from 2,10,
3. He/She does not deal with anything else while teaching, increased to 2,30 from 1,90,
4. He/She always tells the truth, increased to 2,55from 2,10,
5. He/She approves what the teacher says and does, increased to 2,60 from 2,13,
6. 6-He/She is not offended to teacher, increased to 2,45 from 2,18,

b) 2nd part: Inappropriate behaviors towards class mates,

1. He/She interacts with friends, increased to 2,51 from 2,16,
2. He/She does not insult his friends, increased to 2,60 from 2,17,
3. He/She does not make fun of your friends' faults, increased to 2,50 from 2,13,
4. He/She does not always object to what your friends say and do, increased to 2,65 from 2,17,
5. He/She is not offended to friends, increased to 2,55 from 2,34,
6. He/She does not fight with his friends, increased to 2,65 from 2,33,

7. He/She does not prevent your friends from working in the class, increased to 2,54 from 2,23,
 8. He/She does not try to force his friends to accept his ideas, increased to 2,56 from 2,24,
 9. He/She respects the rights of your friends, increased to 2,54 from 2,22,
 10. He/She cooperates with his friends, increased to 2,48 from 2,12,
 11. He/She does not complain about constantly teaching your friends, increased to 2,49 from 2,18,
 12. He/She does not make friends kinky jokes, increased to 2,55 from 2,13,
 13. He/She does not harm friends' items, increased to 2,65 from 2,17,
 14. He/She does not exclude opposite gender in classroom activities, increased to 2,43 from 2,14,
- 3rd part: Inappropriate behaviors towards themselves,
1. He /She follows the entrance and departure times, increased to 2,54 from 2,16,
 2. He /She does not leave the class without permission, increased to 2,65 from 2,17,
 3. He /She does not damage the equipment, increased to 2,45 from 2,20,
 4. He /She does not bring cutter drilling tools, increased to 2,65 from 2,12,
 5. He/She performs the duties of the school, increased to 2,55 from 2,18,
 6. He /She does not cheat on exams, increased to 2,76 from 2,19,
 7. He/She does not refuse to take part in social events, increased to 2,53 from 2,17,
 8. He/She completes the work he started, increased to 2,54 from 2,12,
 9. He/She asks an approval from teacher, increased to 2,57 from 2,18,
 10. He/She does not walk around in class without any cause, increased to 2,58 from 2,15,
 11. He/She does not steal anything, increased to 2,70 from 2,18,
 12. He/She does not spit around, increased to 2,80 from 2,19,
 13. He/She does not write anything on walls, increased to 2,60 from 2,19,
 14. He/She does not use slang language, increased to 2,65 from 2,17,
 15. He/She does not lie, increased to 2,67 from 2,12,
 16. He/She does not eat his/her fingernails, increased to 2,69 from 2,11,
 17. He/She does not pick nose, increased to 2,68 from 2,10,
 18. He/She does not act overly nervous, increased to 2,69 from 2,14,
 19. He/She fulfills his responsibilities, increased to 2,65 from 2,11.

When examined the results after appropriate activities, we can see that their mean results at three parts (1st part: Inappropriate behaviors towards teachers. 2nd part: Inappropriate behaviors towards class mates 3rd part: Inappropriate behaviors towards themselves) increased.

4. Comments and Suggestions

As we examine the study as a whole, we can see that the project had a positive effect on students' behavior. The study shows that for primary school students group counseling activities used by school counselor teacher were useful at detecting and changing

problem behaviors. It also contains study activities and shows that it was indeed successful. In classrooms, students are the ones who behave inappropriately and as a result at the same time they are the victims. In order to solve these problems, students and teachers worked together as a group and teachers guided students in this path. Therefore, this study represents one of the small number of action researches made on this topic. Also, while questioning how to deal with inappropriate student behaviors using group counseling, it also contributed to counseling field. The activities used in this project should be used by other schools so that we can see more widespread results.

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